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A RETROSPECTIVE AND PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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Abstract:

Background: Maternal vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy has numerous health implications in both the mothers and their offspring, therefore, it is important to prevent women from vitamin D deficiency during this period. In India, with high levels of sunlight, pregnant women have been reported to be at increased risk of vitamin D deficiency because of skin exposure to sunlight, oral intake of vitamin D from both foods and supplements, an individual's vitamin D status is affected by his or her sun exposure behavior, such as time spent outdoors, clothing coverage and sunscreen use, as well as dietary behavior. In consideration of the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in pregnant women, it is important to understand how pregnant women behave in regard to sun exposure and vitamin D intake.

Methods: This is retrospective and prospective observational study which is being carried out 6 months and to determine vitamin D deficiency in pregnant women. This study focused on treatment and improve the vitamin D levels in pregnant women by initial therapy.

Results: A total of 100 cases prospective, 200 retrospectives were collected, analyzed and categorized based on vitamin D status, age and BMI. We analyzed that 22-28 age group were highly affected with vitamin D deficient. In our study vitamin D deficiency is caused by many factors includes full clothing (87%), obesity (80%), Region Urban (80%), Skin pigmentation dark skin(100%), Religion(80%).According to our study most of the pregnant women with vitamin D deficiency were observed with associated disorders include diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion:

In our study shows that among them majority are vitamin D deficient. This study has identified possible explanations that may prevent women in India from obtaining adequate vitamin D during pregnancy to assess the knowledge regarding importance of vitamin D among antenatal mothers, to prevent vitamin D deficiency related risk factors in pregnant women.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Diabetes Mellitus, Pregnancy, BMI.

Introduction:

Vitamin D is a complex hormone system known to be involved in bone metabolism and vitamin D can be synthesized by our skin under the effect of sunlight, Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin which includes both vitamin D2 and vitamin D3 are collectively called as calciferol. It is a pro-hormone with its active form calcitriol. Vitamin D3 is three times more effective and has a longer half-life than vitamin D2. Vitamin D can be synthesized by our skin under the effect of sunlight. The reasons cited for high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in our country despite favourable natural conditions are increased skin melanin pigment, less outdoor activity, vegetarian diet, wearing of more covered clothing. The active form of vitamin D 1, 25(OH)₂D works through a binding nuclear receptor, VDR that results in a conformational change in the VDR which allows it to interact with specific DNA sequences.

Physiology:

Vitamin is made in the skin (or) ingested cholecalciferol is hydroxylated in the liver at the position 25 to 25 hydroxy cholecalciferol (calciferol or 25(OH) D. This reaction is catalysed by vitamin D 25-hydroxylase the product of the CYP2R1 Human gene and expressed by hepatocytes. Calcifediol is released into the plasma, where it is bound to an alpha-globulin carrier protein named the vitamin D binding protein named. Calcifediol is transported to the proximal tubules of the kidneys where it is hydroxylated at the 1-alpha position to form calcitriol. It is catalysed by the enzyme, 25-hydroxy vitamin D3 1-Alpha hydroxylase which is the product of the CYP27B1 human gene. The activity of CYP27B1 is increased by parathyroid hormone and also by low calcium phosphate.

Metabolism: Vitamin D is absorbed with other dietary fats in the small intestine. The main pathway of vitamin D uptake is incorporation into chylomicrons that reach systemic circulation via the lymphatic 'S' The product of vitamin D metabolism are excreted through the bile into faces and very little is eliminated through urine

Factors Affecting Production: Skin pigmentation, latitude, Dressing code, Aging, Sunscreen use, Air pollution.

Factors Affecting Absorption: Diet, malabsorption syndrome, celiac disease, chronic pancreatitis, cystic fibrosis.

Materials and Methods:

This is a retrospective (200) and prospective(100) observational study was carried out for a period of six months with a sample size of 300 patients in pregnant women with vitamin D deficiency visiting outpatient department in Jayalakshmi Hospital, JPN road, Warangal were enrolled in this study with an inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria, along with source of data. In this statistics are reported in a descriptive manner for prevalent outcome, association between socioeconomic status food habits and pregnancy number will be analysed using binomial logistics regression.

Results and Discussion:

Vitamin D deficiency is one of the most common conditions in pregnant women. Women with vitamin D deficiency present with diverse features including hypothyroidism, hypertension, and diabetes. A total of 300 cases (Prospective-100, retrospective-200) were reviewed, analysed and categorized based on vitamin D status, age group, BMI, region, diet and skin pigmentation. In our study based on vitamin D status deficient (80%), sufficient (20%) (Table.3, Fig.2), similarly in retrospective study deficient (83%), sufficient (17%). (Table.18, Fig.17).

In prospective study, we analysed that the percentage of 22-28 years was 87% (Table.4, Fig.3) similarly in retrospective study, we analysed that percentage of 15-25years 59.5% age group were highly deficient (Tab.19, Fig.18).Several clinical studies have examined the factors associated with the development of vitamin D deficiency, in which obesity is the factor (Therese Carlson, Louise Anderson, Ayesha et al).In our study we found that women with vitamin D deficiency with overweight (81%) and obese(80%) (Table.5, Fig.4)

According to cross-sectional study on vitamin D deficiency in pregnant women most deficiency is observed in urban than rural (Anwar, M.P. Iqbal et al) in the same way majority of the study population is observed vitamin D deficiency in urban(80%) compared to rural (73%)(Tabke.6, Fig.5) Daniel Gluss, Veronique conducted a study related to pigmentation and Vitamin D metabolism, light skin types have lower levels of 25(OH) D compared to darker skin types. In our study we found that fair skin types have lower levels of vitamin D (81%) compare to darker skin types (100%).(Table.7, Fig.6).

In prospective study vitamin D deficiency is most commonly seen in muslim population(80%) rather than Hindu population(78%) (SH Dijkshtra, A Van Beek et al).(Table.8, Fig.7) .A study on vitamin D deficiency described that women wearing full clothing (87%) have high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency compared to normal (75%) (SH Dijkshtra, A Van Beek et al).(Table9, Fig.8).

A few studies explained the bacterial infection in pregnant women. Among them a study observed bacterial infection in the first trimester of the pregnancy (Bodar LM, Krohn MA) and this infection leads to increase in WBC count. (Tab 10, Fig.9). In our study, majority of population with vitamin D deficiency were observed in first trimester (100%) and the vitamin D deficiency gradually decreases by therapy in second trimester and third trimester (Tab.11, Fig.10).

In our study, the women with low vitamin D status in early pregnancy was associated with a significantly increased risk of associated disorders such as hypertension(100%) and diabetes (100%) that was independent of race, age, religion and material weight.(I. Parle, IL. Bromberg, DS Feign et al.) Conducted a study which includes low serum 25(OH) in early pregnancy has increased risk of associated disorders (hypertension, diabetes), similarity in retrospective study higher increased risk of associated disorders (Tab.12, Fig.11).

We observed that anaemic condition in pregnant women with vitamin D deficiency (Table.13, Fig.12). Out of 100 cases of vitamin D deficiency, D₂ D₃ calciferol(84%) oral tablet was prescribed once daily and calcitriol (82%) oral tablet prescribed once daily. Among them D₂D₃ calciferol tablet was mostly prescribed to pregnant women with vitamin D deficiency. (Table.14, Fig).

Out of 28 cases of vitamin D deficiency, D₂D₃ calciferol (84%) oral tablet was prescribed once daily and calcitriol (82%) oral tablet prescribed once daily. Among them D₂D₃ calciferol tablet was mostly prescribed

K. Visalakshi**et al.* /International Journal of Pharmacy & Technology
 with iron and multivitamin (20%) out of 10 cases (Tab.15, Fig.14) People with vitamin D deficiency, cefixime
 is an antibiotic given for infection out of 15 cases 12 are prescribed with cefixime(70%) and similarly
 cephalixin(67%) is given for infection (Tab.16, Fig.15).

In case of management of associated disorders similarly as study says low vitamin D levels has significant
 increased risk of associated disorders, levothyroxine with dose 100mg was prescribed once daily in 4 cases,
 levothyroxine was prescribed once daily in 8 cases. Gestational diabetes mellitus have effective risk in vitamin
 D deficiency pregnant women out of 10 cases 9 are vitamin D deficient was prescribed with insulin glargine
 once daily. In case of hypertensive condition (Pre-eclampsia), Febatalol was prescribed with 200mg once daily.

Limitations: Difficulty in analyzing the effect of vitamin D deficiency levels prescribed doses given in D2, D3
 calciferol who visited the hospital less than three times

Table-1: Patient demographics (n=100).

Vitamin D Status	No. of cases
Deficient (20-29/ml)	80
Sufficient (30-40ng/ml)	20
AGE	No. of cases
18-21	23 (78)
22-28	56 (87)
29-37	21 (61)

Conclusion:

In our study shows that among them majority are vitamin D deficient. This study has identified
 possible explanations that may prevent women in India from obtaining adequate vitamin D during pregnancy.

The most common age in prospective study is 22-28 years and in retrospective 15-25 years with vitamin D
 deficient .Obesity is the factor which leads to vitamin D deficiency among them overweight or obese undergoes
 high vitamin D cases in pregnant women.

There are some influencing factors that may affect pregnant women’s vitamin D related behaviours, such as
 educational levels, residential region and season. The amount of vitamin D acquired from food is low among
 pregnant women. Pregnant women in India spend limited time outside. When in the sun, they would like to
 cover, on average, 60% of body surface

In our study concluded that high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in dark skin compared to light skin in study population. Full clothing has high vitamin D deficiency in women compared to normal because of limited exposure irrespective of religion, age and weight.

Lower vitamin D status in early pregnancy was associated with a significantly increased risk of subsequent gestational diabetes the was independent of race, age, season and maternal weight. This study suggests that vitamin D may influence glucose tolerance during pregnancy and provides support for studies of vitamin D as a potential intervention to prevent gestational diabetes.

Pregnant women with Vitamin D deficiency has increased risk of Cardio vascular system, coronary artery disease, increased stroke, Heart attack and infection rate. Vitamin D deficiency in pregnant women is an burning problem that needs careful assessment, regular checkups and adequate treatment in order to prevent rickets in new born, premature birth and risk of asthma in child.

Table-2: BMI in study population (n=100).

BMI	No. of cases (%)
Normal	60(78)
Overweight	22(81%)
Obese	5(80%)

Fig-2: Distribution based on vitamin D Status.

Table-3: Rural and urban study (n=100).

Region	No. of cases
Rural	15 (73%)
Urban	85 (80%)

Fig-3: Distribution based on age:

Table-4: Religion in study population.

Religion	No. of cases(%)
Muslim	35(80)
Hindu	65(78)

Fig-4: BMI in study population

Table-5: WBC count in study population.

WBC count	No. of cases
Normal Range	7(71)
Abnormal Range	26(80)

Fig-5: Vitamin D deficiency in rural and urban.

Table-6: Co-morbidities in study population.

Co-morbidities	No. of cases
Diabetes mellitus	10
Hypertension	03

Fig-6: Skin pigmentation in vitamin D deficiency women.

Table-7: Skin pigmentation in vitamin D deficiency women (n=100).

Skin pigmentation	no. of cases	Vitamin D def.	Percentage(%)
Normal	61	47	77
Fair	37	30	81
Black	2	2	100

Fig-7: Religion in study population.

Table-8: Religion based on vitamin D deficiency in study population (n=100).

Religion	No. of cases	Vitamin D def	Percentage (%)
Muslim	35	28	80
Hindu	65	51	78

Fig-8: Pattern of clothing in women.

Table-9: Pattern of clothing in women (n=100).

Clothing	no. of cases	Vitamin D def	Percentage (%)
Normal	68	51	75
Full	32	28	87

Fig-9: WBC count in study population.

Table-10: White blood cells (WBC) count study population (n=100).

WBC count	No. of cases	Vitamin D def	Percentage (%)
Normal range: 4500-11500	7	5	71
Abnormal range: 11600-21300	26	21	80

Fig-10: Period of trimester and vitamin D deficiency in study population

Table-11: Period of trimester and vitamin D deficiency in study population(n=100).

Trimester	No. of cases	Vitamin D def.	Percentage (%)
First	3	3	100
Second	95	75	78
Third	2	1	50

Fig-11: Co morbidities observed in study population in relation with vitamin D deficiency.

Table-12: Co-morbidities observed in study population in relationship with vitamin D deficiency(n=100).

Co-morbidities	no. of cases	Vitamin D deficiency	Percentage (%)
Hypothyroidism	15	14	93
Diabetes	10	10	100
Hypertension	3	3	100
No associated disorders	72	55	76

Fig=12: Hemoglobin levels in study population

Table-13: Hemoglobin levels in study population (n=100).

Hb levels (g/dL)	No. of cases	Vitamin D def.	Percentage (%)
<11	28	24	85
11 to 15	72	55	76

Fig-13: Pharmacological Therapy for vitamin D deficiency.

Table-14: Pharmacological Therapy for vitamin D deficiency (n=100).

Tablet	No. of cases	Vitamin D def.	ROA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
D ₂ D ₃ calciferol	75	63	PO	OD	84
calcitriol	76	63	PO	OD	82
Calcium aspartate	61	50	PO	OD	50
Cholecalciferol	39	35	PO	OD	35

Fig 14: Management of anemia:

Table-15: Management of anemia (n=28).

Tablet	no of cases	Vitamin D def	ROA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Folic acid +iron	28	24	PO	OD	85
Ferrous ascorbate	13	11	PO	OD	84
Iron and multivitamin	10	02	PO	OD	20

Fig-15: Management of infection.

Table-16: Management of infection(n=65).

Tablet	No. of cases	Vitamin D def.	Dose	ROA	Frequency	Infection	Percentage (%)
Cephalexin	44	32	500 mg	PO	BD	31	72
Cefixime	21	16	200 mg	PO	BD	15	76

Fig-16: Management of co-morbidities.

Table-17: Management of Co morbidities (n=100).

Co morbidities	Tablet	no. of cases	Vitamin D def	Dose	ROA	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hypothyroidism	Levothyroxine	04	04	100 mg	PO	OD	100
	Levothyrosine	08	07	-	PO	OD	87
Diabetes	Insulin glargine	10	09	-	PO	OD	90
Hypertension	Fabetalol	03	03	200 mg	PO	OD	100

Fig-17: Distribution according to Vitamin D status.

Table-18: Distribution according to vitamin D status.

Vitamin D status	No. of cases
Vitamin D deficiency	166
Vitamin D sufficiency	34

Fig-18: Demographic profile of study population.

Table-19: Demographic profile of study population (n=200).

Age	No of cases	Percentage%	Vit D deficiency
15-25 yrs	119	59.5	103
26-33yrs	71	35.5	58
34-48yrs	10	05	05

Fig-19: Religion and Vitamin D deficiency in study population.

Table-20: Religion and vitamin D deficiency in study population(n=100).

Religion	No. of cases	Percentage%	Vitamin D deficiency
Hindu	155	83	130
Muslim	45	80	36

Fig-20: Associated disorders and their vitamin D deficiency in study population.

Table-21: Associated disorders and their vitamin D deficiency observed in study population (n=200).

Associated disorders	No. of cases	Percentage %	Vitamin D def.
Hypothyroidism	11	5.5	11
Hyperthyroidism	11	5.5	11
Diabetes mellitus(DM)	03	1.5	03
Hypertension(HTN)	03	1.5	03

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